

Studies in Furan Derivatives. Part III*. Synthesis of Some Furoacenaphthene Derivatives

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Furo (4',5': 4,5) acenaphthene and its 3'-methyl and 3'-phenyl derivatives have been synthesised by the condensation of ethyl bromo-acetate with 4-formyl-4-acetyl-, and 4-benzoyl-5-hydroxy acenaphthene respectively and subsequent hydrolysis, cyclisation and decarboxylation of the 3-carboethoxymethoxy acenaphthene formed. Further α -pyrone(3',6': 4,5) acenaphthene has been synthesised by the Perkin acetylation of 4-formyl-5-hydroxy acenaphthene, and its 4' methyl derivative by the Fickmann condensation of 5-hydroxy acenaphthene with ethyl acetoacetate.

The present work deals with the synthesis of furo (4',5': 4,5) acenaphthene and its 3'-methyl and 3'-phenyl derivatives which do not appear to have been synthesised so far. 5-Hydroxyacenaphthene required for this purpose was synthesised by nitration of acenaphthene to 5-nitroacenaphthene followed by reduction¹ and treatment of the amino derivative with sulphuric acid according to Rapoport *et al.*² 5-Hydroxy acenaphthene on formylation with hexamine in acetic acid gave the 4-formyl derivative which gave an intense greenish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and on Perkin acetylation, and Knoevenagel condensation with diethylmalonate, afforded α -pyrone derivatives thus establishing the *o*-hydroxy-aldehyde structure.

4-Formyl-5-hydroxy acenaphthene was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the 5-carboethoxy-methoxy derivative was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid. On heating with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride the acid underwent simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation furnishing furo (4',5': 4,5) acenaphthene (Ia)

(I)

- Ia, R=H, R'=H
 b, R=CH₃, R'=H
 c, R=CH₃, R'=COOH
 d, R=C₆H₅, R'=H

(II)

- IIa, R=CH₃, R'=H
 b, R=CH₃, R'=Br
 c, R=H, R'=H
 d, R=H, R'=COOC₂H₅
 e, R=H, R'=COOH

*Part II, this Journal,

1. Morgan and Stanley, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 48, 344T.

2. Rapoport *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2719.

4-Acetyl-5-hydroxyacenaphthene, prepared according to Richter and Foist³, through a similar series of reaction gave 3'-methyl furo (4',5':4,5) acenaphthene (Ib). The same product was also obtained by an alternate route as follows: 5-hydroxyacenaphthene was condensed with ethyl acetoacetate to get 4'-methyl- α -pyrono (5',6':4,5) acenaphthene (IIa). The α -pyrono structure was confirmed by conversion into β -methyl β -4 (5-methoxy acenaphthenyl) acrylic acid.

This was then brominated to the 3'-bromo-derivative (IIb). On heating with alkali, it afforded 2'-carboxy-3'-methyl furo (4',5':4,5) acenaphthene (Ic) which on decarboxylation gave (Ib).

5-Benzoyloxyacenaphthene on Fries migration gave 4-benzoyl-5-hydroxyacenaphthene as evidenced by the intense brownish colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the 5-carboethoxy-methoxy derivative obtained was converted to 3'-phenylfuro (4',5':4,5) acenaphthene (Id) by heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride.

EXPERIMENTAL*

4-Formyl-5-hydroxyacenaphthene.—5-Hydroxyacenaphthene (1.7 g.) was heated in acetic acid (50 ml.) with hexamethylene tetramine (5 g.) on a steam bath for 4 hr. Hydrochloric acid (1:1, 10 ml) was added and the heating continued for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. On cooling, needles separated, which were recrystallised from alcohol in needles (1.7 g.), m.p. 95°. It gave intense red colour with conc. H₂SO₄ (Found: C, 78.87; H, 5.17. C₁₇H₁₀O₂ requires C, 78.77; H, 5.05%).

2,4-Dinitrophenyl hydrozone, prepared as usual, was crystallised from nitrobenzene, and had m.p. 284° (decomp.) (Found: N, 14.54; C₁₀H₄O₅N₂ requires N 14.81%).

α -Pyrono (5',6':4,5) acenaphthene (IIa). The above aldehyde (1 g.) was heated at 170-180° with freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) in an oil bath for 15 hr. It was then poured on crushed ice and the solid obtained was crystallised from dil. alcohol in needles, (0.4 g.), m.p. 172-73°. (Found: C, 80.74; H, 4.27. C₁₅H₁₀O₂ requires C, 81.08; H, 4.50%).

3'-Carboethoxy- α -pyrono (5',6':4,5) acenaphthene (IIb).—A mixture of 4-formyl-5-hydroxy acenaphthene (1 g.), diethyl malonate (0.8 g.) and two drops of piperidine was kept overnight at room temperature. The mixture was decomposed by dil. HCl. The separated solid crystallised from benzene in bright yellow needles (0.6 g.), mp. 205°. (Found: C, 73.44; H, 4.49. C₁₈H₁₄O₄ requires C, 73.48; H, 4.76%).

3-Carboxy- α -pyrono (5',6':4,5) acenaphthene (IIc).—The above ester (0.8 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide (5%; 40 ml.) on a steam bath for 3 hr. The solid obtained on acidification was crystallised from benzene in greenish yellow needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 256° (decomp.). (Found: C, 72.14; H, 3.70. C₁₆H₁₀O₄ requires C, 72.18; H, 3.75%).

3. Richter and Foist., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 3133.

*All the m.p.'s are uncorrected.

Decarboxylation—A pinch of copper powder was added to the above acid (0.5 g.) dissolved in quinoline (5 ml.) and the mixture was heated on a sand bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. It was then filtered hot and on adding HCl (1:1; 10 ml.) the α -pyrone acenaphthene separated out which was crystallised from dil. alcohol (0.3 g.), and had m.p. and mixed m.p. with a sample described above was 172-73°

4-Formyl-5-carboethoxymethoxyacenaphthene.—4-Formyl-5-hydroxyacenaphthene (1 g.) was refluxed on a steam bath with ethyl bromoacetate (0.9 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone for 3 hr. Acetone was removed and water was added. The solid obtained crystallised from petroleum ether in needles (1.0 g.), m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 72.18; H, 5.78. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.83; H, 5.68%.)

4-Formyl-5-carboxymethoxy acenaphthene.—The above ester (1 g.) was heated on a steam bath with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide for 3 hr. The product obtained on acidification was purified through sodium bicarbonate, crystallised from benzene, and had m.p. 174°. (Found: C, 70.54; H, 4.70. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 70.33; H, 4.68%.)

Furo(4',5': 4,5)acenaphthene (Ia).—The above acid (1.0 g.) was refluxed on a sand bath with freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice. The separated solid crystallised from dil. ethanol in white flakes, (0.4 g.), m.p. 48°. It gave red colour with conc. H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 87.07; H, 4.77. $C_{14}H_{10}O$ requires C, 86.60; H, 5.16%.)

4-Acetyl-5-carboethoxymethoxyacenaphthene.—4-Acetyl-5-hydroxyacenaphthene (2 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (1.6 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) in dry acetone on a water bath for 3 hr. The ester obtained on adding it to water was crystallised from petroleum ether in needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 75-76°. (Found: C, 72.13; H, 5.98. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 72.47; H, 6.04%.)

4-Acetyl-5-carboxymethoxyacenaphthene.—The above ester (1 g.) was heated on a boiling water bath with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide for 3 hr. The acid obtained on acidification was crystallised from benzene, and had m.p. 168°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 71.41; H, 4.83. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.11; H, 5.18%.)

3'-Methyl-furo(4',5': 4,5)acenaphthene (Ib).—The above acid (1.0 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride for 3 hr. The product was worked up as before and crystallised from dil. ethanol (0.5 g.) and m.p. 57-58°. It gives orange colour with conc. H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 86.28; H, 5.60. $C_{15}H_{12}O$ requires C, 86.54; H, 5.76%.)

5-Benzoyloxyacenaphthene.—5-Hydroxyacenaphthene (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (10%; 10 ml.) and was treated with benzoyl chloride (1 ml) with vigorous shaking. The benzoyl derivative obtained was crystallised from ethanol in flakes (1 g.), m.p. 105°. (Found: C, 83.12; H, 4.86. $C_{19}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.20; H, 5.10%.)

4-Benzoyl-5-hydroxyacenaphthene.—The above benzoyl derivative (2 g.) was dissolved in dry carbon disulphide and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) was added. The mixture was gently refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. The supernatant clear liquid was decanted

and the paste was treated with ice and HCl. The solid separated was crystallised from petroleum ether in bright red prisms, (0.8 g.), m.p. 126°. It gives red colour with sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 83.70; H, 4.85. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.20; H, 5.10%.)

4-Benzoyl-5-carboethoxymethoxyacenaphthene.—The above ketone (2 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (1.8 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone on a steam bath for 4 hr, and the reaction mixture worked up as usual. The separated solid was crystallised from petroleum ether as light yellow flakes (1.8 g.), m.p. 125–26°. (Found: C, 76.30; H, 5.42. $C_{23}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 76.67; H, 5.55%.)

4-Benzoyl-5-carboxymethoxyacenaphthene.—The above ester (1.5 g.) was heated on a steam bath with sodium hydroxide (10%) for 3 hr. The acid obtained was crystallised from benzene (0.8 g.) and had m.p. 174°. (Found: C, 75.82; H, 4.66. $C_{21}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 75.91; H, 4.81%.)

3'-Phenylfuro (4',5':4,5)acenaphthene (Id).—The above acid (0.8 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride for 3 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from ethanol in bright yellow flakes (0.3 g.), m.p. 88°. It gave intense green fluorescence with conc. H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 88.78; H, 5.26. $C_{20}H_{14}O$ requires C, 88.88; H, 5.18%.)

4'-Methyl- α -pyreno (5',6':4,5)acenaphthene (IIa).—Sulphuric acid (80%; 40 cc.) was added to a mixture of 5-hydroxyacenaphthene (2 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (2 cc.) with cooling. The mixture was left over-night. It was then poured on crushed ice and the separated solid crystallised from benzene in needles (1 g.), m.p. 221°. (Found: C, 80.87; H, 5.11. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 81.36; H, 5.68%.)

β Methyl- β -4(5-methoxyacenaphthenyl) acrylic Acid.—4'-Methyl- α -pyreno (5',6':4,5)acenaphthene (1 g.) was dissolved in a boiling mixture of acetone (100 ml) and sodium hydroxide (10%; 20 cc.) and to this solution dimethyl sulphate (2 ml.) was added slowly with continuous shaking. More of alkali and dimethyl sulphate was added and finally the mixture was heated on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. after making the solution alkaline. Acetone was removed and the solution was acidified. The acid obtained was crystallised from petroleum ether, and had m.p. 177°. It decolourised bromine water and alkaline potassium permanganate.

4'-Methyl-3-bromo- α -pyreno (5',6':4,5)acenaphthene (IIb).—The above α -pyreno derivative (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) by warming. It was then cooled and a 10% solution of bromine in acetic acid (7 ml.) was added with constant stirring. The mixture was kept for 3 hr. It was then poured into water. The separated solid crystallised from acetic acid in needles (1 g.) and had m.p. 298°. (Found: Br, 25.64. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2$ Br requires Br, 25.37%.)

2'-Carboxy-3'-methyl furo (4',5':4,5)acenaphthene (Ic).—The above bromo-derivative (2 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide (75 ml.; 10%) on a steam bath for 8 hr. The product obtained on acidification was purified through bicarbonate and crystallised from toluene, yield 0.3 g., m.p. 247°. (Found: C, 75.74; H, 4.89. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.19; H, 4.76%.)

Decarboxylation.—The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed in quinoline (5 ml.) with a pinch of copper powder for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. It was then filtered and dil. HCl was added to the filtrate. The product obtained was crystallised from dil. ethanol, m.p. and mixed m.p. with 3'-methyl furo(4',5': 4,5) acenaphthone described above was 57-58°.

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